

Geoscience DeVL

A vast collection of previously incompatible geoscience datasets are now accessible, to allow researchers to ‘see through new glasses’.

The Geoscience Data-enhanced Virtual Laboratory (DeVL) provides researchers with seamless access to data, tools, compute resources and related services via a single portal.

“For a long time, we have been making data downloadable from a network of geological data stores, but to be able to bring together datasets from all over Australia into a single integrated Big Data platform, and transform the data to be ready for new tools, software and analysis methods is a huge step forward.” Dr Tim Rawling CEO AuScope.

Header image courtesy of Professor Brent McInnes.

Start date

19 December 2017

Expected completion date

31 January 2020

Investment by ARDC

\$625,000

Co-investment partners

[CSIRO](#)

[University of Queensland \(UQ\)](#)

[Curtin University of Technology](#)

[University of Sydney \(USyd\)](#)

[AuScope](#)

[Geoscience Australia \(GA\)](#)

[The University of Melbourne](#)

[University of Tasmania \(UTAS\)](#)

[The University of Adelaide](#)

[National Computational Infrastructure \(NCI\)](#)

[Research School of Earth Sciences \(RSES\)](#)

[ANSIR Research Facilities for Earth Sounding](#)

[Thermochronology and Noble Gas Geochronology and](#)

[Geochemistry Organisation \(TANG3O\)](#)

[State and Territory Geological Surveys](#)

Lead node

2. Passive seismic datasets available

Seven datasets from the ANU Research School of Earth Science (RSES) are accessible through the AusPass Data Portal.

4. International Geo Science Sample Number (IGSN)

Australian researchers are able to apply globally unique identifiers to their samples due to the development of the IGSN. The IGSN service is accessible from the AuScope website, which represents a major feat and enables the broader Geoscience researcher community to properly identify samples. This new service enables the community to improve the auditability of research with unique, global identification of physical specimens. A promotion and training strategy will be developed for the new IGSN Service.

6. A refreshed and updated Virtual Geophysics Laboratory (VGL)

8. Improved discoverability

Increased visibility of Passive Seismic data in the AusPass portal; Increased geographic discoverability of the locations of IGSNs allocated by GA,CSIRO and ARDC in the Australian IGSN portal (<http://igsn.org.au>) and/or a layer in the AuScope Discovery portal; Increased visibility and discoverability of AuScope-funded software; Increased discoverability of Geophysics data services in the NCI and RDA online catalogues using agreed best practice for the relevant international standards.

1. Magnetotellurics (MT) datasets available

Twenty one MT datasets from The University of Adelaide are now discoverable through the NCI GeoNetwork and harvested by Research Data Australia to enable broader discoverability; improved metadata and quality of data using the Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reuseable (FAIR) principles.

3. Magnetic, gravity and radiometric surveys available

Approximately 3000 individual magnetic, gravity and radiometric surveys from Geoscience Australia are accessible from NCI, and are also visible and processable in VGL. The availability of these datasets has greatly increased the number of datasets available via the VGL and to the computational geophysics community.

5. HPC-enabled geophysics software available

The software on NCI enables Australian researchers to discover and deploy geophysics software on Cloud services.

7. A common landing page for all AuScope services

This page brings together all of AuScope's virtual components, including the AuScope Grid, VGL, Underworld2 training, AusPASS and IGSN minting apps. Further services/portals will be added as they become available.

9. Improved service

Bulk uploading to be added to the IGSN service. Production service for HPC MT data operational at NCI. Improve VGL service to enable multiple front ends to interact with the backend.

MT and Passive Seismic data collections

Major Australian academic MT and Passive Seismic data collections are now programmatically accessible online and discoverable through internationally compliant catalogue services.

Global identifiers

Development of infrastructure for academic researchers to use globally unique identifiers for their physical samples, and enabling the samples to be discovered online and linked to analytical data derived from them.

Simplified access to AuScope services

A web portal for all AuScope services has been created and existing services modernised, such as the VGL, to enable Australian researchers to discover and deploy geophysics software and workflows.

Who is this project for?

Academic, industry, government and citizen sectors.

What does this project enable?

- Academic researchers now have a means of storing and making data accessible from future geophysical experiments enabled by ANSIR MT and Passive Seismic instruments.
- Access to an online network that integrates geochemical and geochronological data collected using multiple techniques from multiple Australian institutional laboratories – through the globally unique identifiers service).
- Open access to **geology**, **geochemistry** and **geophysics** data for users of varied backgrounds and skill sets. The **AVRE** facilitates data, software and workflows to be added to trusted repositories, then offers access to these as services either via Virtual Laboratories (for less technical users,) or by user-created Python notebooks to give greater flexibility and foster more innovation and creativity.

Handy resources

- View the final report [10.5281/zenodo.4278996](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4278996)
- Visit [AuScope Virtual Research Environment \(AVRE\)](#)
- View the [Australian Passive Seismic Server](#)
- Learn more about the [International Geo Sample Number \(IGSN\) Minting Service](#)
- Discover datasets at the [NCI GeoNetwork](#)

CSIRO

VISIT

University of Queensland (UQ)

VISIT

Curtin University of Technology

VISIT

<p>Geoscience Australia (GA)</p> <p>VISIT</p>		
<p>The University of Adelaide</p> <p>VISIT</p>		
<p>ANSIR Research Facilities for Earth Sounding</p> <p>VISIT</p>		
<p>Thermochronology and Noble Gas Geochronology and Geochemistry Organisation (TANGSO)</p> <p>VISIT</p>	<p>State and Territory Geological Surveys</p>	

[HOME](#)

[ABOUT US](#)

[SERVICES](#)

[COLLABORATIONS](#)

[NEWS & EVENTS](#)

[CONTACT US](#)

[PRIVACY POLICY](#)

[TERMS & CONDITIONS](#)

The Australian Research Data Commons is enabled by NCRIS.

Stay up to date with our latest news and events and subscribe to our newsletter.

[SUBSCRIBE](#)